

Appendices

Appendix A: studies included in the systematic review

1. Adlakha, D.; Parra, D. C. Mind the gap: gender differences in walkability, transportation, and physical activity in urban India. *Journal of Transport & Health*, v. 18, 2020.
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Appendix B: Number of studies by metric radii sizes and type of buffer.

Note. Studies with multiple radii sizes were counted multiple times.

Appendix C: tables of results

Table 1. Measures for the dependent variables. In parenthesis, the number of studies that adopted each type of measure.

Measure	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Total time spent walking (typically in minutes) in a specified amount of time (usually week or day). (20)	1; 8; 10; 11; 15; 28; 32; 34; 41; 46; 47; 49; 50; 53; 52; 55; 56; 58; 60; 61
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing choice of walking versus other mode choice in trips made in the last X days. (9)	5; 7; 19; 26; 30; 33; 36; 48
Number of walking trips in a specified amount of time. (9)	4; 6; 12; 15; 18; 39; 42; 45; 61
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing any walking (usually of 10 minutes or more) in a given period (typically 1 week). (8)	9; 17; 23; 28; 37; 42; 43; 51; 57
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing choice of walking versus other mode choice for principal means of transportation. (7)	14; 13; 16; 20; 22; 44; 59
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing whether an arbitrary minimum amount of time (typically 150 minutes) was spent walking in a specified amount of time (typically 1 week). (7)	3; 28; 31; 33; 38; 40; 47
Pedestrian counts. (4)	24; 25; 27; 29
Number of days per week with walking activity of at least 10 minutes. (3)	9; 47; 49
Distance walked between transit stops and non-home-ends. (1)	54
Walk share of each trip purpose. (1)	21
Percentage of people who use walking as their primary mode of transportation (1)	35

Table 2. Data sources for land use measures.

Land use data sources	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Official agencies	7; 10; 15; 19; 20; 18; 25; 26; 27; 29; 31; 32; 36; 38; 40; 44; 48; 49; 47; 50; 55; 56; 57; 58; 60; 61
Questionnaire (NEWS and its variants)	2; 1; 3; 6; 5; 8; 11; 12; 13; 16; 28; 35; 37; 39; 41; 45; 46; 51; 52; 59
Field surveys	3; 12; 14; 16; 17; 21; 22; 23; 24; 30; 33; 45; 46; 53; 59
Private agencies	37; 61
Previous studies	9
Google Street View	43
Not reported	4; 34; 33; 42; 54

Table 3. Land use categories for classifications of up to six uses.

Number of land use categories	Reference number (see Appendix A)
2 categories	
Category 1: agricultural, residential. Category 2: commercial, forest, industrial, public, rural.	19
Residential, nonresidential.	30; 29; 43; 47; 48
Stores, facilities.	51
3 categories	
Residential, retail, civic.	9
Residential, commercial, industrial / institutional.	15
Category 1: agricultural / residential; Category 2: commercial / industrial; Category 3: Forest / public / rural.	19
Residential, public [offices and institutions], commercial.	31
Residential, retail, office.	34
Residential, commercial and employment destinations, recreation	35
Convenience (i.e., convenience store, newsagent, or petrol station), supermarket, public transport stop	37
Commercial, residential, office.	22; 23; 60
Night uses (restaurants, bars, theaters, sports arenas), physical activity uses (parks, playgrounds, athletic properties), social uses (religious and cultural areas, playgrounds, athletic properties).	38
Residential, commercial, public.	42
Daily-activity neighborhood use, non-daily commercial use, office.	47
4 categories	
Residential, retail, commercial, industrial, others.	4
Category 1: agricultural / residential; Category 2: commercial / industrial; Category 3: forest / rural; Category 4: public.	19
Residential, commercial, recreational, institutional.	26
Residential, commercial/institutional, recreational and other	45
Residential, commercial, office, others.	24; 25; 44
Commercial, civic (education and hospital/medical), industrial, residential.	37
Residential, retail, office, recreational.	33
Residential, commercial, industrial, others.	36
Residential, commercial, industrial, recreational.	56
5 categories	

residential, commercial, educational, entertainment and public services	8
Residential, commercial, industrial/institutional, recreational, others.	15
Retail, commercial, civic, recreation (excluding public open space), residential	37
Residential, daily neighborhood life, non-daily use, office, others.	48
Residential, recre-ational, commercial, industrial, others.	55
Residential, retail (up to 90,000 m2), entertainment (including restaurants), office, institutional.	50
6 categories	
Residential, commercial, office, public, recreational, others.	49
Residential, eating/drinking, green spaces, recreation centers, social infrastructure, retail.	58
Single family residential, multifamily residential, commercial, office, industrial, green space)	10

Table 4. Spatial units used to aggregate land use mix variables.

Spatial units	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Areas (typically aerial or network buffers) around survey respondents' homes.	2; 3; 4; 6; 8; 9; 12; 13; 15; 20; 21; 22; 23; 33; 38; 40; 44; 45; 46; 47; 49; 50; 51 52; 28; 55; 56; 57; 58; 59; 61
Zones and administrative boundaries	11; 16; 17; 24; 30; 31; 32; 34; 33; 35; 36; 39; 48
Areas around origins, destinations and (sometimes) routes of trips.	5; 7; 14; 19; 18; 26; 53
Observation points along streets.	29
Areas around rail-based transit stations.	42
Areas around transit egresses	54

Table 5. Measures of land use mix.

Measures of Land Use Mix	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Evenness measures	
Shannon entropy with varying land use types (typically 3-6)	4; 5; 7; 8; 9; 10; 15; 16; 19; 20; 18; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 31; 32; 34; 33; 37; 41; 42; 44; 49; 47; 48; 50; 54; 55; 56; 57; 58; 59; 60; 61
Simpson's measure of evenness	19
Heip's index of evenness	19
Smith–Wilson evenness index	19
Bhat and Gossen land use mix diversity measure	19; 36; 18
Hill's ratio	19
Activity-related complementarity	18
Richness measures	
NEWS LUM Diversity: aggregate index representing how distant or close (as subjectively estimated by participants) are non-residential uses (typically 13) to participant's home.	2; 1; 3; 12; 14; 13; 17; 28; 39; 52; 46; 53
Number of different types of land uses within the spatial unit.	4; 38
Proxy measures	
NEWS LUM Access: Aggregate index representing the perception of how easy it is to get to non-residential uses and transit stops around participants' homes or workplace.	1; 11; 12; 14; 13; 17; 28; 51; 52; 53
Density or concentration of non-residential uses ^a	23; 30; 33; 40; 48; 52; 56; 58
Proportion of non-residential uses: index of the type a/b, where "a" represents counts or total area of non-residential uses (typically retail) and "b" is the total count or area of all uses.	29; 37; 43; 45
Intensity of non-residential uses	38
Jobs-housing balance: ratio of jobs-to-housing units	18
Dichotomous variable representing census tract as job concentrator (most units are intended to run industrial or commercial activities, or institutional services) or mixed (more than one use, in a homogeneous proportion).	30
Sinergy measures	
Interaction measure: lines representing the interactions between two distinct uses	35
Composite (factor-based) measures	
Factor with three and five measures of land use mix or balance.	7
Land use mix construct: latent construct including composition and configuration of land uses	20

Notes. ^a This can be calculated through different methods: a) index of the type a/b, where "a" represents counts or total area of non-residential uses (typically retail) and "b" is the area of the spatial unit (typically the buffer) or the area of all other uses; b) clusters analysis capturing significant concentrations of non-residential uses in specific areas; c) average distances from each NR building to all other NR buildings.

Appendix C: Entropy formula (Frank et al., 2005)

$$D_E = -\frac{\sum_i^N p_i \cdot \ln(p_i)}{\ln(N)}$$

Where:

D_E = Entropy measure of diversity.

p_i = proportion of use i .

N = total number of uses.